

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE ORAL HEALTH KNOWLEDGE ACCORDING TO THE REGIONS

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Abstract

Health is the universal human necessity for every group of society. For assessment of the general health condition it is significant to assess the oral cavity health. No less important is to assess the level of knowledge. Accordingly, the goal of our research was to evaluate the level of knowledge. The research was held in Tbilisi dental clinics. The material was collected based on the questionnaires, drawn up by us. The knowledge level about the oral cavity issues is low among the patients. In standard variation the level is lower than the medium one. In different patient groups there were different levels of knowledge. Statistically significant difference was observed among the employed and unemployed men/women. As a result of our research we have found, that the knowledge level, concerning the oral cavity hygiene and the oral diseases, was comparatively high among the men and employed patient groups.

Keywords: oral health, knowledge level, health determinant, awareness.

Introduction

Health is an universal human need that applies to all levels of the social hierarchy. The oral health status is important for the assessment of the general health condition. Assessment of the level of knowledge is of equally importance.

The aim of the present research was to evaluate the extent of oral health knowledge. The research was conducted in the dental clinics of Tbilisi and Rustavi, the material was collected using the survey-questionnaires, designed and prepared by us.

The level of oral health knowledge among patients is low, falling below the average standard across the entire spectrum of variation. The level of knowledge appeared to be different among the patient groups; statistically significant differences were observed between the employed and unemployed individuals, as well as females and males.

The study revealed that the level of knowledge about both oral hygiene and oral diseases is relatively high among the males as well as the employed patient group.

The aim of the present research is to explore and assess the extent of oral health knowledge among the population of Tbilisi and Rustavi.

Materials and Methods:

Selection Methodology: the persons involved in the research were selected among the patients of the dental Clinics in Tbilisi and Rustavi.

The research inclusion criteria encompassed:

- Patient age: 17 years and above;
- First visit to the clinic;

- Ability to speak, write and read Georgian.

Upon meeting the research inclusion criteria, patients were provided with a questionnaire. (Amornphimoltham P, et al., 2011). The distinctive aspect of this process was that the patients independently completed the questionnaire without any assistance. This approach also served as a benefit during the pilot phase. On one hand, it prevented from bias at filling in, and on the other hand, it gave the opportunity to reveal the difficulties that may arise in the process of implementing this type of research.

Based on this, a special approach has been developed: as it is known, dental and soft tissue diseases are leading among oral diseases, in particular, caries, its complications and periodontal diseases. (E. Borovsky. et al., 2010), Both nosologies can be prevented and managed effectively. Through examination of the oral cavity, it is possible to identify the precise location and distribution of the defect. (E. Borovsky. et al., 2010) The survey carried out on the selected sample was based on the questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose. The questionnaire was based on the international experience existed in global practice of researching this specific issue. The questionnaire, as a research tool, was developed encompassing all necessary aspects to effectively measure the phenomenon under study and to achieve the goals and objectives of the research. (Announcement: NIDCR Supplement to the Journal of Public Health Dentistry on Behavioral and Social Intervention Research Essentials, 2014). The survey questionnaire was of mixed type, including closed-ended and open-ended questions. The responses

received for the questionnaire survey were assessed using a points-based system and 2 main gradations were given: 1 point for each correct answer and 0 point for incorrect answer, respectively. (Aida J, et al.,2014)

The level of knowledge was assessed in 3 categories:

- ▶ No knowledge 0-3 points;
- ▶ Average knowledge 4-10 points;
- ▶ Proficient Knowledge 11-20 points.

Here, it should be noted that incorrectly circled answers, that is, not non-circled, but wrongly circled answers were classified as "incorrect" knowledge and were assigned "0" point. Hence, the possible versions were interpreted as "Proficient knowledge", "Average knowledge" and "No knowledge", including erroneous knowledge in the last category.

▶ The data collected through the survey were entered into the database and subjected to statistical processing, using descriptive statistics.

▶ The mean and standard deviations were calculated, the comparison between the groups was carried out through correlation coefficients and χ^2 test, after calculating the coefficients, the p value was recorded.

▶ During the research, 3600 questionnaires were handed out in the districts of Tbilisi and Rustavi, according to which the number of patients was distributed as follows:

- ▶ Krtsanisi - 1440 primary patients;
- ▶ Vake - 120 primary patients;
- ▶ Saburtalo - 720 primary patients;
- ▶ Rustavi - 1320 primary patients.

437 patients refused to participate in the study, and the questionnaire filled by 612 patients was incomplete, and these patients and their data were withdrawn from the research. Ultimately, 2551 survey-questionnaires were fully completed and the data derived from them were incorporated into the database. The structure of the interviewed patients presented here was based on the characteristics investigated in the groups of women and men. These characteristics encompassed employment, education and social status.

The female patients, interviewed according to the employment status, were distributed as follows: out of 1816 interviewed women 307 were employed in the state structures, 580 - in the private sector, 420 were self-employed, 137 had their own business, 314 - housewives, and 58 - unemployed, respectively.

Distribution of the male patients, interviewed according to their employment status: 87 out of 735 interviewed men were employed in the state structures, 210 - in the private sector, 170 were self-employed, 250 had their own business, and 18 were unemployed, respectively.

Distribution of the patients interviewed according to their educational status:

Among the women interviewed:

1. Completed secondary education – 618;
2. Incomplete secondary education – none;
3. Completed higher education - 598;
4. Incomplete higher education - 138;
5. Vocational and technical education - 432;
6. Scientific degree - 27;

7. Master's degree – 3.

Among the men interviewed:

1. Completed secondary education – 187;
2. Incomplete secondary education – none;
3. Completed higher education – 318;
4. Incomplete higher education – 13;
5. Vocational and technical education – 214;
6. Scientific degree – 1.

Distribution of the patients interviewed according to social status:

1. Married - 998 women and 408 men;
2. Single - 422 women and 218 men;
3. Divorced - 128 women and 94 men;
4. Civil marriage - 249 women and 13 men
5. Widowed - 19 women and 2 men.

The Results:

Following the characterization of the study population, the next step involved evaluating their knowledge level regarding oral health. The survey results showed the followings:

- 0 -3 points - 677 women and 180 men
- 4-10 points - 733 women and 274 men
- 11-20 points - 406 women and 281 men

According to the results of the research, 34% of the interviewed patients had no knowledge about the oral health, 39% demonstrated average knowledge, and only 27% of the interviewed patients were acquainted about the oral health (have knowledge).

Consequently, the surveyed patients were predominantly composed of individuals who either had no knowledge about oral health or possessed an average knowledge. Only a small percentage of the respondents have knowledge about the oral health.

The fact that the percentage of oral health knowledge was higher among interviewed men in comparison to women piqued particular interest. To verify our practical assumption, statistical analysis on the acquired data has been conducted. The resultant findings were as follows:

Statistical Analysis of Materials:

Data processing using χ^2 -test showed that the respondents with 0-3 points - "no knowledge" were more reliably identified in the group of women compared to men.

$$\chi^2 = 38,367$$

$$p < 0.0001$$

There was no significant distinction observed between the groups when analyzing the data of respondents with 4-10 points - "average knowledge"

$$\chi^2 = 2.0836$$

$$p = \text{NNS (non-significant - unreliable)}$$

Similar to that of the groups of women and men, the knowledge levels were categorized and presented according to employment, education, and social status.

The data for respondents scoring between 11-20 points - "knowledge," showed a statistically significant difference between the groups of women and men, and women's sample displayed lower knowledge levels.

$$\chi^2 = 72,599$$

p<0.001

Consequently, following the analysis of data extracted from the questionnaires of interviewed patients (Arantes R, et al., 2010), the following information has been obtained: the interviewees generally demonstrated a low level of oral health awareness, the patients either don't have or have an average and insufficient knowledge. Among the respondents, the level of knowledge is reliably higher among men compared to women. This important fragment of the research would be of little value without the second equally crucial part, complementing and completing our research on informing population about oral health and highlighting its significance.

During the research process, after assessing the awareness of the population and gauging their level of knowledge, disparities in oral health were identified among the groups of interviewed patients.

After studying oral health in patients with varying levels of knowledge (high and low), the following findings have been revealed:

Oral health was measured by DMFT (decayed, missing, and filled teeth) (E. Borovsky. et al., 2010), gingivitis (M. Iveriel, et al., 2012) and periodontal indices: (M. Mamaladze, et al., 2011.)

Measured by DMFT index

- ▶ Low level was found in 1302 patients (51.0%),
- ▶ Medium level - 321 patients (12.6%),
- ▶ Satisfactory - 928 patients (36.4%).

To assess the oral health status, the following criteria were used - the correlation between the DMFT index categories and the knowledge assessed by questionnaire scores. This research revealed a strong and statistically significant inverse correlation between the DMFT index and the questionnaire scores - $r = -0.8150$, $p < 0.001$.

The correlation between the gingivitis index and the level of knowledge assessed by questionnaire scores has been measured. This research showed that the gingivitis index has a reliable inverse correlation with the latter - $r = -0.5913$, $p < 0.001$

The correlation between the periodontal index and the level of knowledge assessed by questionnaire scores has been measured. This research also showed that the gingivitis index has a reliable inverse correlation with the latter - $r = -0.2963$, $p < 0.001$

Obtained Results and Discussion

Based on the research findings, it can be affirmed that there is a statistically significant association between the oral health status and the level of knowledge

within the interviewed group. Moreover, analyzing the groups categorized by knowledge level (poor, average, and good), it became evident that the patient groups with poor and average knowledge exhibited poor oral health, and this correlation proved to be statistically reliable.

The level of knowledge among the patients surveyed regarding oral health issues is low.

A total of 34% have no knowledge about the oral cavity, while 39% possess an average level of knowledge. Only 27% of the respondents have information about oral health status, with lower awareness observed among women compared to men.

There is a statistically significant association between oral health status and the knowledge level; In the groups of individuals with poor and average knowledge, oral health tends to be poor, while in those with good knowledge, the relationship between the oral health state and the level of knowledge was not statistically reliable. This implies that poor knowledge is evidently a contributing factor to poor health.

References

1. Aida J, Kondo K, Yamamoto T, Hirai H, Nakade M, Osaka K, Sheiham A, Tsakos G, Watt RG. 2011; Oral health and Cancer, cardiovascular, and respiratory mortality of Japanese. *J Dent Res.* 90(9):1129–35.
2. Amornphimoltham P, Masedunskas A, Weigert R. 2011; Intravital microscopy as a tool to study drug delivery in preclinical studies. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 63:119-28.
3. Announcement: NIDCR Supplement to the Journal of Public Health Dentistry on Behavioral and Social Intervention Research Essentials. 2014;
4. Approved Products - Gardasil. 2014;
5. Arantes R, Santos RV, Frazão P. 2010; Oral health in transition: the case of Indigenous peoples from Brazil. *Int Dental J.* (3S2):235–40.
6. Therapeutic Dentistry Edited by E. Borovsky. 2010. Dental Caries.
7. Therapeutic Dentistry Edited by E. Borovsky. 2010. Changes in oral mucosa at gastrointestinal (GI) diseases
8. Therapeutic Dentistry Edited by E. Borovsky. 2010. Morbidity.
9. Therapeutic Dentistry Edited by E. Borovsky. 2010. Prevention of dental diseases.
10. M. Iveriel, N. Abashidze, Kh. Gogishvili, N. Gogebashvili. 2012. Oral mucosal diseases.
11. M. Mamaladze, N. Korsantia, L. Sanodze. 2011. Operative odontology.